

Imports as a Percentage of GDP in Europe

Between 2010 and 2021 they grew by 16.12%

The Eurostat calculates the value of the import in percentage of GDP in European countries.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the import in percentage of GDP in 2021.

Luxembourg is in the first place for the value of the import in percentage of GDP with a value of 176.70%, followed by Malta with a value of 136.90%, and from Ireland with a value of 95.00%. In the middle of the standings there are Bulgaria with a value of 59.60%, followed by Switzerland with a value of 59.50% and by Bosnia with a value of 56.30%. France closes the ranking with a value equal to 31.40% followed by Italy with a value of 30.30% and Norway with a value of 29.30%. On average, the value of imports as a percentage of GDP is 63.85%.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the percentage variation between 2010 and 2021.

Greece is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of imports as a percentage of GDP between 2010 and 2021 with a value of 65.31% equal to an amount of 19.20 units, followed by Cyprus with a value of 42.83% equal to an amount of 25.10 units, followed by Croatia with a value of 41.29% equal to an amount of 15.40 unit. In the middle of the standings there are Austria with an amount of 15.69% equal to an amount of 7.50 units, followed by Lithuania with a value of 15.33% equal to a value of 10.10 units and from the Estonia with a value of 14.72% equal to an amount of 10.10 units. Iceland closes the ranking with a value equal to -4.53% equal to an amount of -1.90 units, followed by Malta with a value equal to -9.28% equal to an amount of -14.00 units and from Albania with a variation equal to an amount equal to -9.67% equal to -4.70 units. On average, the percentage change in percentage of GDP between 2010 and 2021 grew up a value of 17.59% equal to 8.86 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Two Clusters are thus identified thus constituted or:

- *Cluster 1:* Cyprus, Norway, Greece, Serbia, Croatia, Northern Macedonia, Kosovo, Turkey, Albania, Estonia, Iceland, Switzerland, Czech Republic, Poland, Montenegro, Netherlands, Bulgaria, Latvia, Romania, Slovakia, Lithuania, Portugal, Denmark, Sweden, Hungary, Finland, Spain, Italy, Slovenia, France, Bosnia, Belgium, Austria, Germany.
- *Cluster 2:* Ireland, Luxembourg, Malta.

From the median point of view, it appears that the value of the 2-C2 cluster is higher than the value of the 1-C1 cluster. It therefore derives the following system or: $C2 > C1$. From a strictly geographical point of view, it is possible to understand that obviously countries such as Luxembourg, Ireland and Malta being small countries have greater need to resort to imports to supply the population of goods and services.

Network Analysis with Manhattan distance. A network analysis is then performed with the distance of Manhattan. Complex and simplified network structures are revealed. There is a complex network structure made up of Portugal, Finland, Sweden, Germany, Romania. That is:

- Portugal has a connection with Sweden for a value equal to 0.092 units, with Germany for a value equal to 0.12 units with Finland for a value equal to 0.24 units, with Romania for a value equal 0.25 units;
- Sweden has a connection with Germany for a value equal to 0.13 units, with Romania equal to an amount of 0.25 units, with Portugal for a value equal to 0.092;

- Germany has a connection with Sweden for a value equal to 0.13 units, with Portugal for a value equal to 0.12 units, with Finland for a value equal to 0.19 units;
- Romania has a connection with Sweden for a value equal to 0.19 units, with Portugal for a value equal to 0.25 units;
- Finland has a connection with Germany for a value of 0.15 units, with Sweden for a value equal to 0.21 units, with Portugal for a value equal to 0.24 units.

There is a complex network structure made up of Croatia, Poland, Denmark, Austria. Particularly:

- Croatia has a connection with Poland worth 0.25 units;
- Poland has a connection with Croatia worth 0.25, with Denmark worth 0.19;
- Denmark has a connection with Poland for a value equal to 0.19 units and with Austria equal to 0.22 units;
- Austria has a connection with Denmark worth 0.22 units.

There is a complex network structure made up of Italy, Turkey, Spain, Norway, France. Particularly:

- Italy has a connection with Turkey for a value of 0.21;
- Turkey has a connection with Italy equal to a value of 0.21 units, with Spain for a value equal to 0.2 units and with France equal to a value of 0.174 units;
- Spain has a connection with Turkey for a value equal to 0.2 units, with France for a value equal to 0.072 units, with Norway for a value equal to 0.174 units;
- France has a connection with Spain for a value equal to 0.072 units with Turkey equal to a value of 0.174 units, and with Norway for a value equal to 0.17 units;
- Norway has a connection with Spain worth 0.174 and with France worth 0.17.

There is a complex network structure made up of the Czech Republic, the Netherlands, and Slovenia. Particularly:

- The Czech Republic has a connection with the Netherlands equal to a value of 0.26 units;
- The Netherlands has a connection with the Czech Republic for a value of 0.26 units and with Slovenia equal to a value of 0.19 units;
- Slovenia has a connection with the Netherlands equal to a value of 0.19 units.

There are also two simplified network structures, namely:

- Belgium and Hungary have a connection for a value of 0.19 units;
- Bulgaria and Latvia has a connection worth 0.24 units.

Conclusions. The value of imports as a percentage of GDP grew on average for the countries considered between 2010 and 2021 by a value equal to 16.12%, equal to an amount of 8.86 units. This value is due to a set of factors that can be considered, namely: the integration of European markets, the ability of the euro to purchase goods and services, the development of exports from Asian countries. However, it is possible that in the future these elements may be lacking due to the reduction in the value of the euro against the dollar and in the presence of international friction between the USA and China which jeopardize the supply of many tech products as in the case of semiconductor crisis. However, should there be no demand for products from Europe, there could be a further slowdown in international trade and in the growth rate of world GDP. Finally, it must be considered that the phenomenon of offshore production also has a significant value in determining the amount of imports in terms of GDP. However, even in this case the international frictions with Russia and China can have an effect in redrawing the maps of offshoring. The phenomenon of friend-shoring or the relocation that takes place in countries that are part of a block of "friendly countries"

held by pacts and alliances is increasingly widespread, such as in the Western world, in the Commonwealth, and in the European Union.

Declarations

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References

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Exports of Goods and Services in European Countries in the Period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Estimation and Machine Learning Prediction of Imports of Goods in European Countries in the Period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, e-ISSN.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Exports of Knowledge Intensive Services. A Complex Metric Approach (No. 113348). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Export of Medium and High-Tech Products in Europe. University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A. (2022). The Export of High Knowledge Intensity Services of European Countries (No. 112795). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Impact of Patent Applications on Technological Innovation in European Countries. University Library of Munich, Germany.

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). GDP Growth Rate in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7366715>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). GDP at Constant Prices in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7366771>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Labor Productivity in OECD Countries. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7366797>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Perception of the Financial Situation of European Consumers. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7366993>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Evaluation of the Current Production Capacity of Industry in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7367041>

Appendix

**Ranking dei paesi per valore della variazione percentuale delle Importazioni in
Percentuale del PIL tra il 2010 ed il 2021**

Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per
1	Greece	19,20	65,31	20	Estonia	10,10	14,72
2	Cyprus	25,10	42,83	21	Italy	3,40	12,64
3	Croatia	15,40	41,29	22	Bulgaria	6,30	11,82
4	North Macedonia	23,80	40,96	23	Germany	4,40	11,80
5	Serbia	17,80	40,00	24	France	3,30	11,74
6	Türkiye	10,00	39,22	25	Czechia	7,30	11,68
7	Luxembourg	45,70	34,89	26	Bosnia and Herzegovina	5,00	9,75
8	Poland	12,00	28,24	27	Ireland	8,30	9,57
9	Spain	6,40	23,70	28	Switzerland	4,30	7,79
10	Slovenia	14,10	22,31	29	Kosovo	4,70	7,77
11	Slovakia	17,10	22,24	30	Hungary	4,80	6,28
12	Romania	8,30	21,73	31	Finland	2,10	5,66
13	Latvia	11,60	20,98	32	Sweden	1,60	4,04
14	Denmark	8,90	20,41	33	Norway	0,80	2,81
15	Portugal	6,90	18,30	34	Montenegro	-0,50	-0,80
16	Netherlands	11,00	17,83	35	Iceland	-1,90	-4,53
17	Belgium	11,70	15,79	36	Malta	-14,00	-9,28
18	Austria	7,50	15,69	37	Albania	-4,70	-9,67
19	Lithuania	10,10	15,33				

Ranking dei paesi per valore delle importazioni in percentuale del PIL

Rank	Country	2021	Rank	Country	2021
1	<i>Luxembourg</i>	176,70	20	<i>Bosnia and Herzegovina</i>	56,30
2	<i>Malta</i>	136,90	21	<i>Austria</i>	55,30
3	<i>Ireland</i>	95,00	22	<i>Poland</i>	54,50
4	<i>Slovakia</i>	94,00	23	<i>Croatia</i>	52,70
5	<i>Belgium</i>	85,80	24	<i>Denmark</i>	52,50
6	<i>Cyprus</i>	83,70	25	<i>Greece</i>	48,60
7	<i>North Macedonia</i>	81,90	26	<i>Romania</i>	46,50
8	<i>Hungary</i>	81,20	27	<i>Portugal</i>	44,60
9	<i>Estonia</i>	78,70	28	<i>Albania</i>	43,90
10	<i>Slovenia</i>	77,30	29	<i>Germany</i>	41,70
11	<i>Lithuania</i>	76,00	30	<i>Sweden</i>	41,20
12	<i>Netherlands</i>	72,70	31	<i>Iceland</i>	40,00
13	<i>Czechia</i>	69,80	32	<i>Finland</i>	39,20
14	<i>Latvia</i>	66,90	33	<i>Türkiye</i>	35,50
15	<i>Kosovo</i>	65,20	34	<i>Spain</i>	33,40
16	<i>Serbia</i>	62,30	35	<i>France</i>	31,40
17	<i>Montenegro</i>	62,20	36	<i>Italy</i>	30,30
18	<i>Bulgaria</i>	59,60	37	<i>Norway</i>	29,30
19	<i>Switzerland</i>	59,50			

	2021	GEO (Labels)	Cluster	Silhouette
1	85.8	Belgium	C1	0.64187
2	59.6	Bulgaria	C1	0.707563
3	69.8	Czechia	C1	0.687298
4	52.5	Denmark	C1	0.71844
5	41.7	Germany	C1	0.716345
6	78.7	Estonia	C1	0.664847
7	95.0	Ireland	C2	0.448238
8	48.6	Greece	C1	0.711655
9	33.4	Spain	C1	0.707263
10	31.4	France	C1	0.708132
11	52.7	Croatia	C1	0.717185
12	30.3	Italy	C1	0.703341
13	83.7	Cyprus	C1	0.689466
14	66.9	Latvia	C1	0.7061
15	76.0	Lithuania	C1	0.681546
16	176.7	Luxembourg	C2	0.671712
17	81.2	Hungary	C1	0.643494
18	136.9	Malta	C2	0.669473
19	72.7	Netherlands	C1	0.687101
20	55.3	Austria	C1	0.717937
21	54.5	Poland	C1	0.71846
22	44.6	Portugal	C1	0.716603
23	46.5	Romania	C1	0.717669
24	77.3	Slovenia	C1	0.686245
25	94.0	Slovakia	C1	0.570788
26	39.2	Finland	C1	0.715061
27	41.2	Sweden	C1	0.716953
28	40.0	Iceland	C1	0.716682
29	29.3	Norway	C1	0.707844
30	59.5	Switzerland	C1	0.712546
31	62.2	Montenegro	C1	0.703544
32	81.9	North Macedonia	C1	0.694569
33	43.9	Albania	C1	0.717206
34	62.3	Serbia	C1	0.715108
35	35.5	Türkiye	C1	0.705415
36	56.3	Bosnia and Her...	C1	0.715353
37	65.2	Kosovo	C1	0.713312